

Teachers' Positive Discipline in Relation to Learners' Behavior and Academic Engagement

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Abstract:- Positive discipline is an essential factor that teachers need to consider in the teaching-learning process. This study determined the teachers' positive discipline in relation to students' behavior and academic engagement. A descriptive correlational design was used in the study. The respondents of the survey included three hundred thirty-one students from senior high school of Misamis University, Ozamiz city that were selected through stratified random sampling. The Teachers' Positive Discipline Questionnaire, Students' Behavior Questionnaire, and Engagement Questionnaire were used to gather data on the students' perception with regards to teacher's positive discipline, students' positive behavior, and students' level of engagement. Mean, Standard Deviation, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, were the statistical tools used in the study. Results revealed that the teachers' positive discipline was high, and the students' behavior was positive. Positive discipline in the classroom is an influential factor that leads to students' positive behavior. Teachers' positive discipline in terms of students' motivation did not affect the overall behavior of students. On the other hand, teachers' positive discipline in terms of classroom management is an effective factor that affects behavior. Students are highly engaged in different classroom activities whenever a teacher models and reinforces appropriate classroom techniques. Teachers have to attend training and seminars on the implementation of positive discipline since students in basic education still need close guidance and supervision.

Keywords:- Classroom Management, Engagement, Motivation, Positive Discipline, School.

I. INTRODUCTION

Positive discipline is the arrangements in the classroom brought about by rules of conduct democratically determined to engender an environment of consideration. The development of a caring environment and the fostering of a philosophy of respect create a sense of belonging that motivates learning engagement. Teachers who strive to be subject experts and who arrange classroom space and activities in such a way to involve all pupils in active participation contribute to self-realization (van der Merwe, 2016). Moreover, teachers must, therefore, be sensitive not to the covering of the curriculum but to the learning that has taken place in the process. Teachers cannot ignore the students who do not keep pace with the teaching-learning process. Some

students do feel neglected and unwanted in the whole process of the school system. However, they will tend to realize themselves in a better way and develop positive attitudes towards themselves (Sebastian, 2016).

In the study on "Positive Behavior Interventions," the results indicate that Mystery Motivator successfully maintained behavioral performance for two of the three students. Also, for one student, an intervention was further faded such that self-monitoring replaced teacher's feedback for behavior (Miller et al., 2015). Moreover, administrators, teachers, parents, and communities often feel overwhelmed and challenged by students with problem behavior. They want to create schools that are places of learning, not places of struggle with misbehavior (Crone et al., 2015). Teaching students with behavioral problems is a challenge for many teachers, but other teachers can bring out the best for them (Buttner et al., 2015). However, teachers find it challenging to deal with the lack of respect and responsibility, disobedience, aggression, and rejection of authority that were demonstrated by some of the learners in their classroom (de Witt & Lessing, 2015).

Physical punishment in the Dominican Republic and Guyana had negative associations with the literacy skills of children, and positive treatment in the Dominican Republic had a positive correlation with the literacy skills of the girls. Findings are discussed concerning the negative consequences of harsh disciplinary practices on preschoolers' early literacy skills in these developing countries (Dede Yildirim & Roopnarine, 2019). Results are consistent with the conclusion that a positive school climate holds similar benefits of promoting student's engagement and reducing victimization experiences across Black, Hispanic, and White groups (Konold et al., 2017).

In a study on "Teacher Understanding of Classroom Management and Application of Methods for Dealing with Student Misbehavior," it was concluded that the participants experienced various types of misbehaviors within the classroom. Most behavior patterns were similar; however, many behavior issues were different (Alexander, 2015). Furthermore, research has shown positive discipline to be effective in increasing prosocial behaviors between peers in a general education classroom (Turney, 2018).

Consistent and predictable classroom environments, schedules, and routines can increase children's independence, ability to anticipate change, and likelihood of using appropriate behavior. Providing children with specific and positive feedback helps them learn what appropriate behavior looks like. Verbally, commending appropriate behavior as it occurs is an essential tool for classroom management, but teachers can create opportunities for more formal recognition of positive behavior (Hancock & Carter, 2016).

In a study on "Effects of Implementing School-Wide Positive Behavioural Interventions and Supports on Problem Behaviour and Academic Achievement in a Canadian Elementary School," it revealed that a decrease in problem behaviors is essential not only for the benefit of the social environment in the school, but also in the amount of time saved for teaching and learning (Kelm et al., 2015). Furthermore, to promote learning, educators need interventions that teach social and emotional competencies that can reduce behavior problems. Indeed, the emergence of behavior problems has been linked to poor emotional competence of the children, specifically, problems in understanding and regulating emotions (Rose et al., 2015).

It is argued that to sustain positive effects of positive behavior intervention, future implementation efforts need to emphasize administrator support for the school team, ongoing high-quality professional development, and technical assistance (Jung et al., 2017). Therefore, an emphasis on fidelity implementation at the coaching level is important. It is the creation and evaluation of sustainability assessment methods focused on large-scale quantitative international studies and a more rigorous qualitative study. (Yeung et al., 2016). Moreover, experience, through which students learn the sum of conditionally parallel interaction processes that occur as part of interpersonal relations and everyday life with their teacher, through teacher's verbal and non-verbal behavior, has a significant impact on shaping students' behavior and character (Vlah, et al., 2015). Multiple regression analysis shows that teacher's teaching skills and student's learning discipline have a positive and significant influence on student's learning outcomes. To improve the influence of the relationship between two independent variables and one dependent variable, the relationship between teacher and student must be continuously improved so that student learning outcomes can be obtained maximally (Cohen et al., 2019).

The above context draws the concern of this study. Thus, consequently, this study was conducted to determine how the teacher's positive discipline correlates to the students' behavior and their academic engagement in senior high school of the Basic Education Department, Misamis University in Misamis Occidental province.

This study has been beneficial to the the classes in the senior high school. The output has been relevant in maintaining and escalating the students' good performance that ultimately contribute to the improvement of instruction in University.

II. METHODS

❖ *Research Design*

This study used descriptive-correlational design. Correlational research is a type of non-experimental research method in which a researcher measures two variables, understands and assesses the statistical relationship between them with no influence from any extraneous variable. The goal of correlational research is to describe the relationship between variables and to measure the strength of the relationship (Picciano, 2016).

This study was conducted at the different strands of the Senior High School Department, Misamis University during the School Year 2019-2020. The respondents of the study were one hundred six students. They were selected through stratified random sampling.

The study used the following instruments:

- A. Teachers' Positive Discipline Questionnaire. This questionnaire was developed by the UNESCO Office Bangkok and Regional Bureau for Education in Asia and the Pacific (2006) to measure the teachers' level of positive discipline. The instrument involved two dimensions such as classroom management and student motivation.
- B. Student's Behavior Questionnaire. It is a modified and adapted questionnaire from the Child Behavior Survey (Martine et al., 1999). The test had undergone content validation through the research adviser and five other teachers. After the validation process, the instrument was subjected to a pilot test using 30 students who are not included as actual respondents of the study. The research instrument yielded a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.80 as reliability coefficient. Hence, the instrument is valid and reliable to administer to the respondents. It has twenty-eight (28) indicators used to determine the students' behavior in the classroom.
- C. Academic Engagement Questionnaire. It is a modified and adapted questionnaire from Kember and Leung (2009). The test had undergone content validation through the research adviser and ten other teachers. After the validation process, the instrument was subjected to a pilot test using 20 students who were not included as actual respondents of the study. The research instrument yielded a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.80 as reliability coefficient. Hence, it is valid and reliable to administer to the respondents. It has twenty-one (21) indicators. The questionnaire was used in determining the students' academic engagement scale.

The researcher secured a certification and letter of request from the Graduate School of Misamis University. The researcher sought approval from the Office of the Vice President for Academic Affairs for the conduct of study in the University. Then, the approval of the School Principal of the Misamis University, Ozamis City, was obtained for the conduct of the study. The class advisers were informed and asked of the participation of their students as the actual respondents of the study. Informed consent was solicited before the respondents were asked to answer the research

instrument. The researcher personally administered the questionnaires to the respondents to answer any questions and to ensure high percentage of retrieval. The data gathered were tallied and subjected to statistical treatment. Analyses and interpretation of data followed.

The principles of ethical considerations by Bryman and Bell (2007) were complied with within this study. First, the researcher participants were not subjected to harm by any means. Respect for the participants' dignity was prioritized. Full consent was obtained from the participants before the study. Protection of the privacy of research participants, an adequate level of confidentiality of the research data, and the anonymity of individuals participating in the research were ensured. Moreover, deception and exaggeration about the aims and objectives of the study were avoided. Affiliations in any form, sources of funding, and any possible conflicts of interest were declared. Lastly, any communication concerning the research was done with honesty and transparency. Any misleading information, as well as the representation of primary data findings in a biased way, was avoided.

Using the minitab software, the following statistical tools were used:

- *Mean and standard deviation.* These are used in determining the level of the teacher's positive discipline and students' behavior and academic engagement.
- *Pearson r Product Moment Correlation Coefficient.* This was used in exploring the significant relationship between the respondents' positive discipline and students' behavior; and between the respondents' positive discipline and students' academic engagement.

III. FINDINGS

A. Level of the Teachers' Positive Discipline

Data revealed that the teachers' level of implementation of positive discipline was high (M = 3.89; SD = 0.49) (Table 1). This means that teachers had highly implemented positive discipline in the class on students' motivation and classroom management. Through positive discipline, the teachers have motivated and managed their students and sustained their interest throughout their lessons.

Constructs	M	SD	Interpretation
1. Student's Motivation	3.88	0.56	High
2. Classroom Management	3.89	0.42	High
Overall Implementation	3.89	0.49	High

Table 1. Teachers' Positive Discipline

Note: Scale: 4.20-5.0(Very High); 3.20-4.19 (High); 2.61-3.19 (Moderate); 1.81-2.60(Low);1.0-1.80(Very Low)

B. Students' Behavior

Data revealed that the students' behavior was positive (M = 3.76; SD = 0.39) (Table 2). This means that majority of students demonstrate a very positive behavior. They show cooperative attitude and response in classroom activities and discussions. Other positive actions such as showing courtesy and respect to teachers and classmates are some of the positive actions shown that lead to the realization of the class goals.

Since the students rated and perceived their behavior very positively, they were aware that in their stage in life they need to act appropriately to pursue steps higher than what they are doing.

Constructs	M	SD	Interpretation
Students' Behavior	3.76	0.39	Positive

Table 2. Students' Behavior

Note: Scale: 4.20-5.0(Very Positive); 3.20-4.19 (Positive); 2.61-3.19 (Moderate); 1.81-2.60(Negative); 1.0-1.80(Very Negative)

C. Students' Academic Engagement

The data revealed that the students' academic engagement was high (M= 4.05; SD = 0.41) (Table 3). Students were highly engaged in the activities with their peers, teachers, classmates and even technologies used by the teachers in the classroom. Students developed ability to make judgments about alternative perspective. They were aware on their responsibility of their own learning. They are highly interactive in activities assigned by their teachers either in individual, or group assignments. Moreover, students have developed initiative in doing classroom activities.

Constructs	M	SD	Remarks
Students' Academic Engagement	4.05	0.41	Highly Engaged

Table 3. Students' Academic Engagement

Note: Scale: 4.20-5.0(Very High Engaged); 3.20-4.19 (Highly Engaged);(Engaged); 1.81-2.60(Less Engaged);1.0-1.80(Least Engaged)

D. Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Positive Discipline and Students' Behavior

Pearson product Moment Correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between the teachers' positive discipline and students' behavior (Table 4). The data revealed that only the classroom management of the teachers is significantly related to the students' behavior (r = 0.21; p = 0.04) (Table 4). This finding implies that the teachers manage the class well; the students' behavior becomes positive. The data further revealed that teachers' motivation is not related to the behavior of the students. The teachers' motivation in the classrooms is important but the data revealed, it is not statistically significant to the behavior of the individual students. Motivation is not also very evident so that the students' behavior is not very positive. It would mean that despite the motivation done by the teacher extrinsically, the students' behavior is not affected.

Variables	r-value	p-value	Remarks
Student's Motivation and Behavior	0.19	0.07	Not Significant
Classroom Management & Behavior	0.21*	0.04	Significant

Table 4. Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Positive Discipline and Students' Behavior

Note: * means p-value ≤ 0.05; significant at 5% level

E. Significant Relationship Between the Teachers’ Positive Discipline and the Students’ Academic Engagement

Pearson product Moment Correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between the teachers’ positive discipline and the students’ academic engagement (Table 5). The data revealed that the teachers’ positive discipline in terms of student motivation ($r = 0.21$; $p = 0.04$) and classroom management ($r = 0.21$; $p = 0.04$) have significant impact in the academic engagement of the students. This means that when teachers increase the use of motivation and manage a class effectively; they engage in more in class activities.

Variables	r-value	p-value	Remarks
1. Student’s Motivation & Engagement	0.46**	0.00	Highly Significant
2. Classroom Management & Engagement	0.48**	0.00	Highly Significant

Table 4. Significant Relationship Between the Teachers’ Positive Discipline and the Students’ Academic Engagement

Note: * means $p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$; significant at 5% level

IV. DISCUSSIONS

Positive discipline is based on universal principles of living that include connection and encouragement to increase belonging and significance, social interest, motivation through kindness and firmness, skill development, and self-regulation (Nelsen, 2018). Positive classroom climate, expectations, motivation, and methods for constructive reflection on mistakes are investigated to support teachers in developing a positive learning environment (Sieberer-Nagler, 2016). On the contrary, a study revealed that in classes where teachers managed disruptive behaviors by using punitive strategies, students had problems in learning as punitive strategies lowered students’ motivation. Teaching effectiveness was found to mediate the effect of punishment on motivation while motivation mediated the effect of punitive strategies on achievement. The motivation was found to have the most substantial effect on achievement (Rahimi & Karkami, 2015).

Teachers need to ensure that the learners are surrounded by a positive learning atmosphere. A positive learning atmosphere is a more effective way to manage misbehaving students in the classroom rather than using punishment or rewards. Moreover, teachers need to ensure that the learners are surrounded with a learning environment that consists of physical as well as the psychological climate where pupils feel the sense of belongingness. Doing motivational activities and interactive games may help the teachers hold the attention of learners. Also, establishing routines for all daily tasks and needs and including the learners in the planning of class rules and regulations may help build a well-managed class.

Pupils’ behavior is often a reaction to factors prevailing within the classroom (van der Merwe, 2016). If a student is naturally engaging in positive behavior, it is paramount that the teacher encourages these actions with specific and immediate positive attending. Failure to reinforce it may result

in to the students not freely demonstrating similar behaviors in the future (Perle, 2016). Consistent and predictable classroom environments, schedules, and routines can increase children’s independence, ability to anticipate change, and likelihood of doing appropriate behavior. Providing children with specific and positive feedback helps them learn what appropriate behavior looks like. Verbally commending appropriate behavior as it occurs is an essential tool for classroom management, but teachers can create opportunities for more formal recognition of positive behavior (Hancock & Carter, 2016).

To encourage positive behavior, teachers need to be genuine and generous in reinforcing positive behavior. Teachers shall exercise the legitimate power in the classroom; being approachable encourages students to show their positive behavior. Knowing the feeling of the learners is a factor that leads to the achievement of the classroom goals. On the other hand, common misbehavior in the classroom is attention span problem wherein students do not listen during discussion. Teachers shall give short but interesting activity to catch the attention of the learners.

To be genuine, teachers give commendable comments and praise according to merit. By doing this, teachers appreciate and recognize the students’ hard work and ethical behavior.

To have a more engaging learning environment with the students, the teachers need to pay more attention to creating positive opportunities to participate, in terms of both academic activities and peer interaction (Ulmanen et al., 2014). Activities that incorporate emotions, personality characteristics, prior learning experiences, shared values across contexts, technology, and nonacademic aspects shall be planned and implemented well as these influence individual differences in students’ engagement (Wang & Degol, 2014). Researchers and educators have shown a growing interest in the idea of engagement as a means of improving disaffection, preventing student’s frustration, enhancing the motivation and participation of students in school-related activities, the productive student achievement rates, and recognizing the positive growth of students. Results showed that school kindness was positively correlated to agnatic, behavioral, cognitive, and emotional engagement (Datu & Park, 2019). Moreover, strong student’s engagement may develop a mechanism by which interpersonal relationships may connect with academic engagement (Collie-et al., 2016).

Teachers’ actions can influence how students engage in school. Teachers have to shall plan activities and lessons that allow learners to engage with themselves, classmates, teachers, and even instructional technologies. Encouraging them to do metacognition so they can interact with themselves and using interactive and collaborative teaching strategies. By doing this, students may develop their engagement skills with their peers.

It is presumed that students’ optimal positive behavior is attained through effective classroom management techniques employed by the teachers in the learning process. Hence, it is

essential to employ different classroom management techniques to have a good relationship among the students in the class. This is done to have effective teaching and learning and improve the students' behavior.

A decrease in problem behaviors is essential not only for the benefit of the social environment of the school, but also in the amount of time saved for teaching and learning (Kelm, et al., 2015). As part of classroom management, teachers need to orchestrate a smooth transition and continuity of momentum to ensure that every instructional moment is used wisely. School administrators and teachers need to work collaboratively by having school and class rules and regulations that guide the students on how they behave and act (Jung-et al., 2017). In the classroom, the teachers can use effective disciplinary strategies that are proactive for the behavior of students and influential in shaping their behavior and character. These include proximity control, signal interference, removal of seductive objects, and redirection or involving them in another activity (Vlah et al., 2015).

One of the essential roles that teachers play is being a classroom manager. As classroom managers, they need to manage resources to facilitate learning. These resources include time, teaching materials, and other physical features like desks and tables, and the learners themselves. When the pupils are exposed to a well-organized classroom, they behave appropriately.

Teachers' motivation and classroom management play a vital role in the increase in the academic engagement of students in the classroom. It is presumed that students' academic engagement is at the maximum whenever teachers' positive discipline and motivational techniques in the classroom are being utilized effectively. Hence, it is essential to establish positive discipline coupled with techniques in motivation in the classroom to gauge the academic engagement of the students.

Creating a supportive and active learning environment is an essential factor in promoting learning to students. Background knowledge and skills on motivation and classroom management, academic self-regulatory skills, and the experience of teaching staff are factors which are to be considered when endeavoring to increase student academic achievement (Reinke, 2019). An authoritative school climate characterized by disciplinary structure and student support is conducive to positive academic outcomes for middle and high school students. The higher disciplinary structure was associated with higher engagement, and higher student support was associated with higher engagement, and higher student support was associated with higher engagement (Cornell, Shukla, & Konold, 2016).

To achieve maximum engagement from students, teachers shall employ differentiated approaches that increase motivation, and that holds students' attention. These include group activities, peer teaching, cooperative learning, and other interactive activities. Teachers also need to minimize discipline time to maximize engagement and learning in the classroom.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Students behave properly when positive discipline is evident in the classroom. Positive discipline is regarded as the efficient way to manage misbehaving students. It allows students to learn and adapt their behaviors to meet expectations in the classroom. Positive discipline in the classroom is an influential factor that leads students' positive behavior. Teachers' positive discipline in terms of students' motivation did not affect the overall behavior of learners. On the other hand, teachers' positive discipline in terms of classroom management is an effective factor that affects behavior. To encourage positive behavior, teachers shall be genuine and generous in reinforcing positive behavior. To be genuine, teachers give commendable comments and praises according to merit. As classroom managers, teachers shall manage resources to facilitate learning. These resources include time, teaching materials, and other physical features. Moreover, students' are highly engaged in the different classroom activities whenever a teacher models and reinforces appropriate classroom technique.

Based on the findings and conclusion, it is recommended that teachers shall attend training and seminars on the implementation of positive discipline since students in the basic education still need close guidance and supervision. School principal shall plan for the proper trainings and seminars of teachers for the implementation of positive discipline in classroom and even in the whole campus as well. Hence, teachers' discipline creates a substantial impact on the life of the students. This is for the teachers' personal and professional development so that students will realize the value of discipline. Also, teachers shall integrate values in their teaching. This will help students to become a better person in the near future.

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